

STUDY ON ECONOMICALLY PROFITABLE CROPPING PATTERNS IN A SELECTED AREA OF MYMENSINGH DISTRICT

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Abstract

This study was conducted at the Durbachara village at Vangnamari union of Gouripur upazila under Mymensingh district during November 2103 to May 2014. Data were recorded through focus group discussion (FGD) with thirty-three farmers including small, medium and large farm households, school and madrasah teachers and village leaders by using pre-designed check list and structured schedule. There were seven cropping patterns in this village. Farmers earned the highest gross return (Tk.702819) and gross margin (Tk.438534) from the *Vegetable - Vegetable-Vegetable* pattern whereas *Boro-Fallow - T. Aman* pattern produced the lowest gross return (Tk.220216) and gross margin (Tk.43999). There is a scope to incorporate mustard in between *T. Aman* rice and *Boro* rice in *Boro - Fallow - T. Aman* pattern with a little arrangement of rice transplanting times. Farmers are not used to cultivating wheat and inclusion of wheat might be more profitable compared to existing rice based pattern. One pulse crop such as mungbean might be introduced between wheat and *T. Aman* rice as mungbean is more profitable compared to *aus* rice. Thus, *Mustard-Boro-T. Aman* and *Wheat -Mungbean- T. Aman* might be more profitable cropping pattern in Durbachara village.

Key words: Cropping pattern, Economic, Profit, Yield.

Introduction

Economy of Bangladesh is largely based on agriculture which contributes 16.33% to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) at current prices (DAE, 2015). The total cultivable land is estimated to be 8.50 million hectares with an average cropping intensity of 190 percent (BBS, 2014;DAE, 2015). High population growth (1.47%) with low growth in agricultural productivity adversely affects the living standard in the country (BBS, 2014;DAE, 2015). Economic development in Bangladesh cannot be achieved unless there is a breakthrough in the agriculture sector.

The present production of rice cannot meet the total food needs and especially nutrient requirements of the country. Crop diversification is an important issue now-a-days. Wheat is a very good substitute of rice and can play a vital role to feed the people of the country (Kabir and Islam, 2012). The popularity of wheat as a food is gaining momentum year after year and it has reached such a point that very few people in Bangladesh refuse to take as food. On the other hand, wheat, mustard and pulses production needs relatively small quantity of irrigation water and fertilizers as compared to *Boro* rice. Considering these circumstances, the Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh is determined to increase wheat and mustard area and production in the country. In Bangladesh, cultivable land is limited and there is little scope to expand. So, to increase the wheat and mustard production, productivity of the crops should be increased through adoption of improved technologies and cropping pattern might be of one among them.

Cropping pattern simply means the proportion of land area under different crops at a point of time (Punithavathi and Baskaran, 2010). In another word, cropping pattern is the yearly sequence and spatial arrangement of crops or crops and fellow in a given land area (Agrawal and Kassam, 1976). It is dependent on physical, historical, social, institutional and economic factors as well as government policies (Agrawal and Kassam, 1976; Shahidullah *et al.*, 2006). The cropping pattern and the changes therein depend on a large number of factors like climate, soil type, rainfall, agricultural technology, availability of irrigation facilities and other inputs, marketing and transport facilities and growth of agro-industries (Neena, 1998;Gadge, 2003).

A number of cropping patterns are being practiced by the farmers at the Durbachara village of Gouripur upazilla under Mymensingh district. It is very much important to identify the profitability of the major *Rabi* crops based cropping patterns for the farmers of this area. The rate of expansion of crop area and improvement in yield depend on the profitability of cropping pattern.

Detailed information on land situation and cropping systems is a pre-requisite for a fruitful development programme (Shahidullah *et al.*, 2006). Upazilla level office of the Department of Agricultural Extension (DAE) maintains a statistic on individual crop, which has some limitations for getting a real picture of existing cropping patterns and land utilization. Study on profitability of dominant cropping patterns adopted in this area is scarce. Therefore, present study was designed with the following objectives to (i) build up a database on major existing cropping patterns and agronomic practice in the Gouripur upazila of Mymensingh district; (ii) to determine the economically viable dominant cropping pattern and (iii) to identify the scope of incorporating new crop(s) within the existing cropping patterns.

Materials and Methods

The study area was Durbacahra village at Vangnamari union of Gouripur upazila under Mymensingh district of Bangladesh (the latitude of 24.75° N and the longitude of 90.50° E) from November 2013 to May 2014. In the Old Brahmaputra Floodplain dark grey non calcareous alluvium soils are predominant. These soils are mostly sandy loam belonged to Sonatala series under AEZ 9 (Brammer, 1996). Climatic (rainfall and thermal condition) data were collected from the nearest weather station and are presented in Figure 1. Data were recorded through focus group discussion (FGD) with thirty-three farmers including small, medium and large farm households, school and madrasah teachers and village leader by using pre-designed check list and structured schedule. Three classes of farmers were identified according to the farm households. Necessary data, such as farmers' perception about prevailing cropping pattern, crops establishment and harvesting time, detail input use pattern for each crop, identified major cropping pattern, yield of individual crop, per unit prices of relevant input and output were recorded. Descriptive statistical method was used for analyzing data.

Fig. 1. Monthly temperature and rainfall distribution pattern in Gouripur during November 2013 to May 2014

Results and Discussion

Classification of farmers

In the study area three classes of farmers were identified (Table 1). Majority of the farmers were in medium class having 1.0-3.0 hectares land and they occupied 59 percent of FGD group. Small class farmers hold the second position while the large are in third. All of them cultivate their own land. Around 13 percent of small farmers take lease other farmers' land for crop cultivation.

Table 1. Classification of farmers in Durbachara village on the basis of farm size

Class	Farm household (hectares)	Percent of total
Large	>3.0	17
Medium	1.0-3.0	59
Small	0.2-1.0	24

Cropping patterns of Durbachara village

There were seven cropping patterns identified at the Durbachara village (Table 2). Among them, five cropping patterns, such as *Boro* rice-Fallow-*T. Aman*, Vegetables - Vegetables- Vegetables, Vegetables-*Aus* rice- Vegetables, Mungbean- *Aus* rice/ Fallow - *T. Aman* rice and *Boro* rice - *Aus* rice/Jute/Fallow - *T. Aman* rice were practiced pattern at this village. The area coverage by the dominant cropping pattern *Boro* rice - Fallow - *T. aman* was 72% alone (Table 2).

Table 2. Cropping patterns at Durbachara village

Cropping pattern (CP)	Rabi	Kharif I	Kharif II	Area coverage (%)
CP ₁	Boro rice	Fallow	T. Aman rice	72
CP ₂	Vegetables (cabbage/cauliflower)	Vegetables (brinjal)	Vegetables (bottle gourd)	11
CP ₃	Vegetables (sweet gourd /potato)	Aus rice	Vegetables(okra/radish)	8
CP ₄	Mungbean	Aus rice/ Fallow	T. Aman rice	5
CP ₅	Boro rice	Aus rice/Jute/Fallow	T. Aman rice	2
CP ₆	Fallow	Fallow	T. Aman rice	1
CP ₇	Chili	Aus rice/Jute/Fallow	T. Aman rice	1

Variety(s) of different crops used by the farmers

Farmers are mostly dependent on the local market for collecting crop seeds. Most of the farmers are ignorant also indifferent about the varieties. Information on crop varieties was collected based on the discussion with local seed dealer, seed companies and sub-assistant agricultural officer have been presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Varieties used for different crops at Durbachara village

Name of the crop	Name of the variety
Boro rice	BRR1 dhan28, BRR1 dhan29 and local variety (Basiraj)
T. Aman rice	BR11, BRR1 dhan34, BRR1 dhan49, BRR1 dhan52, Bina dhan-7, Hybrid rice and local varieties (Gotairi, Arparina)
Aus rice	Balam (BR16)
Jute	Deshi (BJRI Deshi pat 4)
Cabbage	Topmost, Agroduct (BARI Bandhakopi- 2)
Cauliflower	Rupa (BARI Fulcopi-1)
Brinjal	Kazla (BARI Begun-4), Sadabaigon (BARI Hybrid Begun-4)
Bottle gourd	Local variety (Panilau, Shit lau) of different seed companies collected from local market
Sweet gourd	Local varieties (Chinimisti) of different seed companies collected from local market
Potato	Kufri Sindhuri (BARI Alu-10)
Okra	Local varieties of different seed companies collected from local market
Radish	Local varieties of different seed companies collected from local market
Chili	Local variety (Balojori)
Mungbean	BARI Mung-5

Sowing/planting and harvesting time

Time of sowing is an important factor for getting good yield, especially for all *Rabi* crops. It was found from the Table 4 that usually farmers of the village did not sow their crops within the optimum time. BRR1 recommended optimum time of *T. Aman* rice and *Aus* rice are mid-July to mid-August and mid-March to mid-April, respectively. But farmers transplanted these crops up to end of August and third week of April to second week of May, respectively.

Table 4. Sowing/planting and harvesting time of crops at Durbachara village

Name of crops	Sowing/transplanting time	Harvesting time
<i>T. Aman</i> rice (HYV)	Second week of July to second week of August	Third week of November to second week of December
<i>T. Aman</i> rice (Local)	During August	During December
<i>Aus</i> rice (Local/HYV)	Third week of April to second week of May	Third week of July to second week of August
<i>Boro</i> rice (Local/HYV)	Third week of January to second week of February	First to third week of May
Vegetables (<i>Rabi</i>)	Second week of August	First to second week of December
Vegetables (<i>Kharif I</i>)	Last week of February	First week of August
Vegetables (<i>Kharif II</i>)	Last week of June	Last week of August
Chili	Last week of October to First week on November	Second to third week of March
Mungbean	Third week of January to second week of February	Second week of April to second week of May

Farmers transplanted *T. Aman* rice in late due to inundation of land occurred from the flood water of Brahmaputra river. Farmers usually use long duration varieties of *T. aman* rice due to lack of technical know-how. They transplant *Aus* rice in late because they waited for rains. Farmers were in time to transplant *Boro* rice within the recommendation of BRRI. Farmers sowed mungbean within BARI recommended optimum time.

Cost and returns of individual crops under dominant cropping patterns

This chapter focuses on to determine the costs and returns for different crops under the dominant cropping patterns. For determination of relative profitability of different crops and cropping patterns, it was necessary to compute all cost items for each of the individual crops. Costs of production of individual crops under the dominant cropping patterns are mentioned below:

Land value

Most of the farmers cultivate their own land. Large and medium farmers lease their land to small farmers in exchange of definite amount of money for single season crop cultivation. The leasing value of the land varies according to the seasons have been presented in the Table 5.

Table 5. Leasing value of land per hectare at Durbachara village

Season	Leasing price per 10 decimal land(Tk.)	Leasing price per hectare (Tk.)
<i>Rabi</i>	1200	29640
<i>Kharif I</i>	1100	27170
<i>Kharif II</i>	1100	27170

Human labor cost

Human labor was one of the most important cost items of enterprises under the dominant cropping patterns and presented in Table 6. Per hectare total human labor used for the cropping pattern CP₁ (*Boro* rice - Fallow - *T. Aman* rice) were 120 and 111 man-days where per hectare cost for the respective crops were Tk.30000 and Tk.27750, respectively. The per hectare total human labor used for producing crops in the pattern CP₂(Vegetables- Vegetables-Vegetables) were 140, 129, and 117 man-days, while their corresponding costs were Tk.35000, Tk.32250 and Tk.29250, respectively. For producing Vegetables, *Aus* rice and Vegetables under the pattern CP₃per hectare total human labor costs were Tk. 35000, Tk. 30000 and Tk.35000, respectively. In case of the cropping pattern CP₄ (Mungbean-*Aus* rice-*T. Aman* rice) per hectare total human labor costs were Tk.33000, Tk. 30000 and Tk.27750, respectively. Cropping pattern CP₅ demands a total labor cost of Tk. 87750 to complete the cycle.

Table 6. Per hectare labor cost of individual crops under the dominant cropping patterns at Durbachara village

Cropping pattern (CP)	Man days ha ⁻¹	Unit price per day (Tk.)	Labor cost (Tk. ha ⁻¹)
CP ₁ : <i>Boro</i> rice	120	250	30000
Fallow	--	--	--
<i>T. aman</i> rice	111	250	27750
Total	231		57750
CP ₂ : Vegetables	140	250	35000
Vegetables	129	250	32250
Vegetables	117	250	29250
Total	386		96500
CP ₃ : Vegetables	140	250	35000
<i>Aus</i> rice	120	250	30000
Vegetables	140	250	35000
Total	400		100000
CP ₄ : Mungbean	132	250	33000
<i>Aus</i> rice	120	250	30000
<i>T. Aman</i> rice	111	250	27750
Total	363		90750
CP ₅ : <i>Boro</i> rice	120	250	30000
<i>Aus</i> rice	120	250	30000
<i>T. Aman</i> rice	111	250	27750
Total	351		87750

Ploughing cost

Power tiller was used for tillage operation in the study village. The per hectare costs of tillage operation for *Boro* rice and *T. Aman* rice under cropping pattern CP₁ required total Tk. 15808, whereas pattern CP₂needed Tk. 17125. The tilling cost of pattern CP₃ was Tk.22395,CP₄ was Tk.21077and for CP₅ was Tk. 23712 (Table 7).

Table 7. Per hectare ploughing cost of individual crops under the dominant patterns at Durbachara village

Cropping pattern (CP)	Ploughing number	Price per 10 decimal land (Tk.)	Ploughing cost (Tk. ha ⁻¹)
CP ₁ : <i>Boro</i> rice	3	320	7904
Fallow	--	---	--
<i>T. Aman</i> rice	3	320	7904
Total			15808
CP ₂ : Vegetables	2.5	320	6587
Vegetables	2	320	5269
Vegetables	2	320	5269
Total			17125
CP ₃ : Vegetables	2.5	320	6587
<i>Aus</i> rice	3	320	7904
Vegetables	3	320	7904
Total			22395
CP ₄ : Mungbean	2	320	5269
<i>Aus</i> rice	3	320	7904
<i>T. Aman</i> rice	3	320	7904
Total			21077
CP ₅ : <i>Boro</i> rice	3	320	7904
<i>Aus</i> rice	3	320	7904
<i>T. Aman</i> rice	3	320	7904
Total			23712

Cost of seeds

Per hectare cost of seeds used for *Boro* rice and *T. Aman* rice under the pattern CP₁ were Tk. 1650 and Tk. 1800, respectively, whereas in case of CP₂ (Vegetables-Vegetables-Vegetables) corresponding seed costs per hectare were Tk. 1200, Tk. 1000 and Tk. 900, respectively. For CP₃ (Vegetables-*Aus* rice-Vegetables) seed costs were Tk. 1200, Tk. 1800, and Tk. 1200, respectively, whereas cropping pattern CP₄ (Mungbean - *Aus* rice-*T. Aman* rice) per hectare seed costs were Tk. 1750, Tk. 1800, and Tk. 1800, respectively. In CP₅ seed demands for *Boro* rice was Tk. 1650, *Aus* rice Tk. 1800 and *T. Aman* rice Tk. 1800. Cost of seeds has been presented in the Table 8.

Cost of insecticides

Farmers are used to using insecticides for all crops they grown. Cost of insecticides was found to be the highest for vegetables under the cropping pattern CP₂ and CP₃ which was Tk. 2100 (Table 8).

Cost of irrigation

Farmers used irrigation water for all the crops except Mungbean. Although *T. Aman* rice and *Aus* rice are rain-fed crops, they need to irrigate due to lack of rainfall during cropping season. *Boro* rice demands the highest irrigation cost of Tk. 14820 where mungbean does not require any irrigation (Table 8).

Table 8. Per hectare materials input cost of individual crops under the dominant cropping patterns at Durbachara village

Cropping pattern (CP)	Seed		Insecticides cost (Tk. ha ⁻¹)	Irrigation cost (Tk. ha ⁻¹)	Total (Tk. ha ⁻¹)
	Quantity (kg ha ⁻¹)	Cost (Tk. ha ⁻¹)			
CP ₁ : <i>Boro</i> rice	55	1650	1570	14820	18040
Fallow	--	--	--	--	--
<i>T. Aman</i> rice	60	1800	920	11350	14070
Total		3450	2490	26170	32110
CP ₂ : Vegetables		1200	2100	12000	15300
Vegetables		1000	2100	8000	11100
Vegetables		900	2100	10000	13000
Total		3100	6300	30000	39400
CP ₃ : Vegetables		1200	2100	12000	15300
<i>Aus</i> rice	60	1800	700	11350	13850
Vegetables		900	2100	10000	13000
Total		3900	4900	31350	42150
CP ₄ : Mungbean	25	1750	1800	--	3550
<i>Aus</i> rice	60	1800	700	11350	13850
<i>T. Aman</i> rice	60	1800	920	11350	14070
Total		3750	3420	22700	31470
CP ₅ : <i>Boro</i> rice	55	1650	1570	14820	18040
<i>Aus</i> rice	60	1800	700	11350	13850
<i>T. Aman</i> rice	60	1800	920	11350	14070
Total		3650	3190	38520	45960

Cost of fertilizer

The fertilizer costs for different crops under the dominant cropping patterns are presented in Table 9. The Table shows that for cropping patterns CP₁, CP₂, CP₃, CP₄ and CP₅ per hectare total costs of fertilizer were Tk. 13747, Tk.27280, Tk.22654, Tk. 13380 and Tk.18166, respectively. Total fertilizer cost for the pattern CP₂ was the highest followed by the order of CP₃>CP₅>CP₁>CP₄.

Profitability analysis of the dominant cropping patterns

Per hectare yield, gross return, and profit of the major cropping patterns are presented in Table 10. Under the cropping CP₁ (*Boro* - Fallow - *T. Aman* rice) per hectare total gross return was estimated at Tk. 218408 per year. In this pattern, the total variable costs and profit were Tk. 176217 and Tk.42191, respectively. For cropping pattern CP₂ (Vegetable - Vegetable - Vegetable) per hectare total gross return was estimated Tk. 702819 per year where total variable costs and gross margin were Tk. 264285 and Tk. 438534, respectively. The per hectare gross return of the cropping pattern CP₃ (Vegetable - *Aus* rice - Vegetable) was estimated Tk. 562231 whereas total variable costs and gross margin were Tk. 271179 and Tk.291052, respectively. In case of cropping pattern CP₄ (Mungbean - *Aus* rice - *T. Aman* rice) per hectare gross return was estimated Tk. 285594 while total variable costs and the gross margin were Tk. 240657 and Tk.44937, respectively. Pattern CP₅ (*Boro* rice - *Aus* rice - *T. Aman* rice) earned a profit of Tk.132100 with gross return Tk. 307688 and gross margin Tk. 175588. From these data it is clear that the pattern CP₂ (Vegetables -Vegetables -Vegetables) is the most profitable

pattern of Durbachara village while the cropping pattern CP₁ (*Boro* rice - Fallow - *T. Aman* rice) is the lowest earning pattern might be due to remaining fallow during *Kharif I* season. According to the profitability patterns could be arranged in order of CP₂ (Vegetable - Vegetable - Vegetable) > CP₃ (Vegetable - *Aus* rice - Vegetable) > CP₅ (*Boro* rice - *Aus* rice - *T. Aman* rice) > CP₄ (Mungbean - *Aus* rice - *T. Aman* rice) > CP₁ (*Boro* rice - Fallow - *T. Aman* rice).

Table 9. Per hectare manure and fertilizer cost of individual crops under the dominant cropping patterns at Durbachara village

Cropping pattern (CP)	Urea		TSP		MOP		Gypsum		Total Cost (Tk.)
	Qty (kg ha ⁻¹)	Cost (Tk. ha ⁻¹)	Qty (kg ha ⁻¹)	Cost (Tk. ha ⁻¹)	Qty (kg ha ⁻¹)	Cost (Tk. ha ⁻¹)	Qty (kg ha ⁻¹)	Cost (Tk. ha ⁻¹)	
CP₁:									
<i>Boro</i> rice	197	3349	95	2375	110	1760	100	900	8384
Fallow	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
<i>T. Aman</i> rice	127	2159	52	1352	82	1312	60	540	5363
Total									13747
CP₂:									
Vegetables	300	5100	97	2522	120	1920	112	1008	10550
Vegetables	250	4250	90	2340	100	1600	95	855	9045
Vegetables	200	3400	80	2080	90	1440	85	765	7685
Total									27280
CP₃:									
Vegetables	300	5100	97	2522	120	1920	112	1008	10550
<i>Aus</i> rice	127	2159	50	1300	60	960	--	--	4419
Vegetables	200	3400	80	2080	90	1440	85	765	7685
Total									22654
CP₄:									
Mungbean	44	748	85	2210	40	640	--	--	3598
<i>Aus</i> rice	127	2159	50	1300	60	960	--	--	4419
<i>T. Aman</i> rice	127	2159	52	1352	82	1312	60	540	5363
Total									13380
CP₅:									
<i>Boro</i> rice	197	3349	95	2375	110	1760	100	900	8384
<i>Aus</i> rice	127	2159	50	1300	60	960	--	--	4419
<i>T. Aman</i> rice	127	2159	52	1352	82	1312	60	540	5363
Total									18166

Scope to introduce new crop(s) in the existing pattern

In the pattern CP₁ (*Boro* rice - Fallow - *T. Aman* rice), farmers transplant *T. Aman* rice during the first week of July and harvest during the first week of October. They transplanted *Boro* rice in mid-February. From the month of mid-October to mid-February total four months remain fallow. A crop of around ninety day's duration can easily be cultivated during this fallow period. Mustard is a crop of around ninety days which can easily be fitted between *T. Aman* rice and *Boro* rice and may make this pattern more profitable.

Table 10. Per hectare yield, gross return, gross margin per year of the major cropping patterns at Durbachara village

Cropping pattern (CP)	Crop yield (Kg ha ⁻¹) (i)	Unit price (Tk. Kg ⁻¹) (ii)	Gross return (Tk. ha ⁻¹) (iii)=(i)×(ii)	Total variable cost (Tk. ha ⁻¹) (iv)=Tab.5+Tab.6+Tab.7+Tab.8+Tab.9	Profit (Tk. ha ⁻¹) (iv)-(iii)
CP ₁ : <i>Boro</i> rice	6580	18	118440	93960	24480
Fallow	--	--	--	--	--
<i>T. Aman</i> rice	6248	16	99968	82257	17711
Total			218408	176217	42191
CP ₂ : Vegetables	29484	9	265356	97077	168279
Vegetables	25340	9	228060	84834	143226
Vegetables	23267	9	209403	82374	127029
Total			702819	264285	438534
CP ₃ : Vegetables	29484	9	265356	97077	168279
<i>Aus</i> rice	5467	16	87472	83343	4129
Vegetables	23267	9	209403	90759	118644
Total			562231	271179	291052
CP ₄ : Mungbean	1558	63	98154	75057	23097
<i>Aus</i> rice	5467	16	87472	83343	4129
<i>T. Aman</i> rice	6248	16	99968	82257	17711
Total			285594	240657	44937
CP ₅ : <i>Boro</i> rice	6580	18	120248	93960	26288
<i>Aus</i> rice	5467	16	87472	83343	4129
<i>T. Aman</i> rice	6248	16	99968	82257	17711
Total			307688	259560	48128

Farmers of the Durbachara village claimed that, they are facing irrigation problem during *Boro* rice cultivation due to the absence of rainfalls and sharp lowering the water table of ground water. So a crop of less water consuming during *Boro* season is in demand. Farmers need to apply 5 to 7 irrigations for *Boro* rice. On the contrary, wheat requires 2 to 3 irrigations which may make the wheat cultivation more profitable over *Boro* rice. If farmers sow wheat during the mid to last of November, they will be able to harvest by mid-March. Before transplanting *Aman* rice in mid-July, there is a fallow period of about ninety days. This fallow time can easily be utilized by cultivating a short duration pulse crop such as summer mungbean which earns higher profit margin compared to *Aus* rice (Table 9). After the mungbean harvest farmers can easily cultivate *T. Aman* rice. Thus, Wheat-Mungbean- *T. Aman* might be a more profitable cropping pattern instead of CP₄ (Mungbean - *Aus* rice - *T. Aman* rice) or CP₅ (*Boro* rice - *Aus* rice - *T. Aman* rice) or CP₆ (Fallow-Fallow- *T. Aman* rice).

Conclusion

Among the seven existing cropping patterns in Durbachara village, Vegetable-Vegetable- Vegetable is the most profitable pattern. But cultivation of vegetables in three succession seasons in the same land overtime is detrimental to the soil health. Similarly, three rice crops in three successive seasons can deplete soil organic matter content which is a great challenge for our agriculture. Land used for cultivating three vegetables or three rice need to be changed for the second year. Introduction of wheat and mustard within the existing pattern and thus Wheat-Mungbean- *T. Aman* rice and Mustard - *Boro*- *T. Aman* rice might be more profitable pattern for the Durbachara village. It is crucial to create farmers awareness and arrange training for them regarding to profitable land management with minimal disturbance of soil health. DAE personnel can play a vital role in this concern.

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